

Formulation Evaluation and Development of Essential Oils Containing Anti-Aging and Anti-Wrinkle Skin Care Serum

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ABSTRACT: There is urgent need for Essential oils Containing Anti-aging and Anti-Wrinkle Skin care serum production and from local raw materials in order to supplement the existing ones. I recommend more research to be carried out on extraction of essential oil and its formulation from vast variety of oil bearing plants in our ecosystem. Further work should be carried out to analysis the Essential oil as this could not be done due to time constraint. Characterization of All oils components should be made in order to determine which is responsible for the characteristics of Pungent and Aromatic odor. Furthermore, large scale extraction of Essential oil through enzymatic process should be explored; feasibility studies on the economic viability of the process should be conducted.

Keywords: Vaccume Distillation, flavonoids, Anti-Oxidant, Anti-Aging.

INTRODUCTION: Aging and Wrinkles are natural. As people get of age, their skin gets thinner, drier, and less elastic, and less capable to defend itself from damage. This leads to wrinkles, creases, and lines on the skin. UV light breaks the collagen and elastin fibers in the skin. These fibers form the skin's connective tissue. They are located below the surface of the skin, and they support the skin. Destroy this layer causes the skin to become weaker and less flexible. The skin starts to languish, and crinkles occur. A wrinkle, also known as a rhytide, is a fold, ridge or crease in an otherwise smooth surface, such as on skin or fabric. Skin wrinkles typically appear as a result of ageing processes such as glycation,[1] habitual sleeping positions,[2] loss of body mass, sun damage,[3] or temporarily, as the result of prolonged immersion in water. Age wrinkling in the skin is promoted by habitual facial expressions, aging, sun damage, smoking, poor hydration, and various other factors.[4] In humans, it can also be prevented to some degree by avoiding excessive solar exposure and through diet (in particular through consumption of carotenoids, tocopherols and flavonoids, vitamins (A, C, D and E), essential omega-3-fatty acids, certain proteins and lactobacilli).[5]

Skin aging is a part of a natural human "aging mosaic" which becomes evident and follows different trajectories in different organs, tissues and cells with time. While the aging signs of internal organs are masked from the ambient "eyes," the skin provides first obvious marks of the passing time. Skin aging is a complex biological process influenced by combination of endogenous

or intrinsic (genetics, cellular metabolism, hormone and metabolic processes) and exogenous or extrinsic (chronic light exposure, pollution, ionizing radiation, chemicals, toxins) factors.¹ These factors lead together to cumulative structural and physiological alterations and progressive changes in each skin layer as well as changes in skin appearance, especially, on the sun-exposed skin areas. In contrast to thin and atrophic, finely wrinkled and dry intrinsically aged skin, premature photo aged skin typically shows a thickened epidermis, mottled discoloration, deep wrinkles, laxity, dullness and roughness.¹³⁻¹⁸ Gradual loss of skin elasticity leads to the phenomenon of sagging.¹⁹ Slowing of the epidermal turnover rate and cell cycle lengthening coincides with a slower wound healing and less effective desquamation in older adults. This fact is important when esthetic procedures are scheduled.²⁰ On the other side, many of these features are targets to product application or procedures to accelerate the cell cycle, in the belief that a faster turnover rate will yield improvement in skin appearance and will speed wound healing. A marked loss of fibrillin-positive structures as well as a reduced content of collagen type VII (Col-7), may contribute to wrinkles by weakening the bond between dermis and epidermis of extrinsically age skin. Sun-exposed aged skin is characterized by the solar elastosis. The sparse distribution and decrease in collagen content in photo aged skin can be due to increased collagen degradation by various matrix metalloproteinase, serine, and other proteases irrespective of the same collagen production. In older skin, collagen looks irregular and disorganized, the ratio of Col-3, to Col-1 has been shown to increase, due, significantly, to a loss of Col-1.²⁹ The overall collagen content per unit area of the skin surface is known to decline approximately 1%/year. Glycosaminoglycan's (GAGs) are among the primary dermal skin matrix constituents assisting in binding water. In photo-aged skin, GAGs may be associated with abnormal elastotic material and thus be unable to function effectively. The total hyaluronic acid (HA) level in the dermis of skin that age intrinsically remains stable; however, epidermal HA diminishes markedly. [6, 7] (Deshmukh, et.al 2022

Types of Wrinkles

Sleep wrinkles

Sleep wrinkles are created and reinforced when the face is compressed against a pillow or bed surface in side or stomach sleeping positions during sleep. They appear in predictable locations due to the underlying superficial musculoaponeurotic system (SMAS), and are usually distinct from wrinkles of facial expression. As with wrinkles of facial expression, sleep wrinkles can deepen and become permanent over time, unless the habitual sleeping positions which cause the wrinkles are altered.

Water-immersion wrinkling

The wrinkles that occur in skin over prolonged exposure to water are sometimes referred to as pruney fingers or water aging. This is a temporary skin condition where the skin on the palms of the hand or feet becomes wrinkly. This wrinkling response may have imparted an evolutionary benefit by providing improved traction in wet conditions, and a better grasp of wet objects. These results were called into question by a 2014 study that failed to reproduce any improvement of handling wet objects with wrinkled fingertips. However, a 2020 study of gripping efficiency found

that wrinkles decreased the force required to grip wet objects by 20%, supporting the traction hypothesis.

Prior to a 1935 study, the common explanation was based on water absorption in the keratin-laden epithelial skin when immersed in water, causing the skin to expand and resulting in a larger surface area, forcing it to wrinkle. Usually the tips of the fingers and toes are the first to wrinkle because of a thicker layer of keratin and an absence of hairs which secrete the protective oil called sebum.

In the 1935 study, however, Lewis and Pickering were studying patients with palsy of the median nerve when they discovered that skin wrinkling did not occur in the areas of the patients' skin normally innervated by the damaged nerve. This suggested that the nervous system plays an essential role in wrinkling, so the phenomenon could not be entirely explained simply by water absorption. Recent research shows that wrinkling is related to vasoconstriction. Water probably initiates the wrinkling process by altering the balance of electrolytes in the skin as it diffuses into the hands and soles via their many sweat ducts. This could alter the stability of the membranes of the many neurons that synapse on the many blood vessels underneath skin, causing them to fire more rapidly. Increased neuronal firing causes blood vessels to constrict, decreasing the amount of fluid underneath the skin. This decrease in fluid would cause a decrease in tension, causing the skin to become wrinkly.

Causes for aging wrinkles

Wrinkles are a natural part of the aging process. As people get older, their skin becomes thinner, drier, and less elastic, which means it is less able to protect itself from damage. This leads to wrinkles, creases, and lines on the skin.

Facial expressions, such as smiling, frowning, or squinting, lead to the development of fine lines and wrinkles at a young age. These lines deepen as the person gets older.

When a person is young, their skin springs back. As they get older, the skin loses its flexibility, and it becomes more difficult for the skin to spring back, resulting in permanent grooves.

Wrinkles affect people of different skin tones differently due to structural and functional differences in the skin. Research Trusted Source indicates that the compact dermis is thicker in the skin of Black and Asian people, which likely protects against facial wrinkles.

Many factors affect the development of wrinkles, including:

- sun exposure
- smoking
- dehydration
- some medications
- environmental and genetic factors

Exposure to ultraviolet (UV) light from sunbathing, tanning booths, and outdoor sports increases the development of wrinkles.

UV light breaks down the collagen and elastin fibers in the skin. These fibers form the connective tissue that supports the skin. As this layer breaks down, the skin becomes weaker and less flexible. The skin starts to droop, and wrinkles appear.

Darker skin contains more melanin and protects from many harmful effects of UV radiation. People who work in sunlight have a higher chance of early wrinkles. Wearing clothes that cover the skin, such as hats or long sleeves, may delay the development of wrinkles. Regular smoking accelerates the aging process of skin because it reduces the blood supply to the skin. Alcohol dehydrates the skin, and dry skin is more likely to develop wrinkles.

Treatment

There are many treatments available to help reduce fine lines on the skin. For deeper creases, a person may require more aggressive techniques, such as plastic surgery or injections of fillers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Methods:

Selection of active:

- Essentials oil of ginger contains actives compounds such as terpens, oleoresin, zingiberol, zingiberone, and zingiberene (23.5%). Camphene, farnesene (12.0%), geraniol, β -bisabolene, neral, β -sesquiphellandrene (10.3%), linalool, α - pinene, citronellal, and bornel.
- Rosemary contains a number of phytochemicals, including rosmarinic acid, camphor, caffeic acid, ursolic acid, betulinic acid, carnosic acid, and carnosol. Rosemary essential oil contains 10–20% camphor.[11,12]

Collection and Authentication:

Oil authentication is a quality assurance process that ensures the correct plant species and plant parts are used as raw materials for herbal medicines. [13] The proper authentication of herbal raw materials is critically important to the safety and efficacy of herbal medicines. Ginger and Rosemary were purchased from local market and authenticated in botanical department by botanist. (Kumar Ganesan. et.al 2016)

Extraction Method:

Vacuum distillation:

Vacuum distillation is distillation performed under reduced pressure, which allows the purification of compounds not readily distilled at ambient pressures or simply to save time or energy. This technique separates compounds based on differences in their boiling points. [14,15] This technique is used when the boiling point of the desired compound is difficult to achieve or will cause the compound to decompose. Reduced pressures decrease the boiling point of compounds. The reduction in boiling point can be calculated using a temperature-pressure nomograph using the Clausius–Clapeyron relation. (Saleem U. et.al 2017)

Soxhlet Extraction:

Soxhlet extraction is a continuous solid / liquid extraction. A solid which contains the material to be extracted is placed in what is called a thimble. A thimble is made out of a material which will

contain the solid but allow liquids to pass through. A lot like filter paper. The thimble containing the material is placed in the Soxhlet extractor. An organic solvent is then heated at reflux. As it boils its vapors rise up and are condensed by a condenser [16, 17]

Selection of base:

The main objective of the present study was to prepare an Anti-aging and Anti-Wrinkle Skin Care Serum Formulation incorporated into the Serum, hence Serum base are used.

Formulation of Hair Growth Serum:

TABLE.1: FORMULATION OF BASE ANTI-AGING AND ANTI-WRINKLES SKIN CARE SERUM

Ingredients	Parts Used	Category	Qty%
Ginger 	Rhizomes	Anti-aging, Anti-Oxidant Anti- Wrinkles	10
Rosemary 	Leaves	Anti-aging, Anti-Oxidant Anti- Wrinkles	10
Hyaluronic acid	–	Gelling agent	3
Triethanolamine	–	Neutralizer	0.3
EDTA	-	Chelating Agent	0.1
Allantoin	-	Emollient	0.2
Propylene glycol	–	Moisturizer	5
Distilled water	–	Vehicle	70.04
DMDM Hydantoin	–	Preservative	1

EXPERIMENTAL WORK:

Extraction of Ginger using Vacuum Distillation

Vacuum distillation is distillation performed under reduced pressure, which allows the purification of compounds not readily distilled at ambient pressures or simply to save time or energy. This technique separates compounds based on differences in their boiling points. This technique is used when the boiling point of the desired compound is difficult to achieve or will cause the compound to decompose. Reduced pressures decrease the boiling point of compounds.[18] The reduction in boiling point can be calculated using a temperature-pressure Industrial-scale vacuum distillation has several advantages.[19,20] Close boiling mixtures may require many equilibrium stages to separate the key components. One tool to reduce the number of stages needed is to utilize vacuum distillation. Vacuum distillation is typically used in oil refineries have diameters ranging up to about 14 meters (46 feet), heights ranging up to about 50 meters (164 feet), and feed rates ranging up to about 25,400 cubic meters per day (160,000 barrels per day). (Neethu Letha, et.al 2016)

Vacuum distillation can improve a separation by:

Prevention of product degradation or polymer formation because of reduced pressure leading to lower tower bottoms temperatures, Reduction of product degradation or polymer formation because of reduced mean residence time especially in columns using packing rather than trays. Increasing capacity, yield, and purity. Another advantage of vacuum distillation is the reduced capital cost, at the expense of slightly more operating cost.[21,22]

FIG. NO.1 - VACUUM DISTILLATION APPARATUS

FIG NO.2-EXTRACTION OF NATURAL OIL BY VACCUME DISTILLATION

Extraction of Rosemary using Soxhletion Methods:

Soxhlet extraction:

Soxhlet extraction has traditionally been used for a solid sample with limited solubility in a solvent in the presence of insoluble impurities.[23] A porous thimble loaded with a solid sample is placed inside the main chamber of the Soxhlet extractor. By refluxing the solvent through the thimble using a condenser and a siphon side arm, the extraction cycle is typically repeated many times.[24] Soxhlet extraction is a rugged, well-established technique and permits unattended extraction. However, it requires a long extraction time and the consumption of a large amount of solvent. Soxhlet extraction is a very useful tool for preparative purposes in which the analyte is concentrated from the matrix as a whole or separated from particular interfering substances.[25] Sample preparation of environmental samples has been developed for decades using a wide variety of techniques.[26,27] Solvent extraction of solid samples, which is commonly known as solid-liquid extraction (also referred to as leaching or Lixiviation in a more correct use of the physicochemical terminology), is one of the oldest methods for solid sample pretreatment. (Monil Yogesh Neena, et.al 2018)

Procedure

FIG. NO 3- EXTRACTION OF NATURAL OIL BY SOXHLETION

Evaluation of extract

Preliminary phytochemical screening:

Flavonoids: To test solution add few drops of NaoH solution formation of dilute acid indicates presence of flavonoids.

Glycosides: A small amount of alcoholic extract of samples is dissolved in 1ml water and then aqueous sodium hydroxide is added. Formulation of yellow colour indicates the presence of glycosides.

Alkaloids (Mayer's test): 1.36gm of mercuric chloride is dissolved in 60ml and 5gm of potassium iodide is dissolved in 10ml of distilled water respectively. These two solvents are mixed and dilute to 100ml using distilled water. To 1ml of acidic aqeous solution of samples few drops of reagent is added. Formation of blue or green colour indicates the presence of alkaloids.[31, 32]

Phenols (ferric chloride test):To 1ml of alcoholic solution of sample. 2ml of distilled water followed by a few drops of 10% aqueous ferric chloride solution is added. Formation of blue or green colour indicates the presence of phenols.

Tannins (lead acetate test):In a test tube containing about 5ml of an aqueous extract a few drops of 1% solution of lead acetate was added. Formation of a yellow or red precipitate indicate the presence of tannin.[33]

Lipids:

In a test tube 5 drops of the sample was taken and a pinch of sodium hydrogen sulphate was added. Pungent odor emanates from the tube which indicates that glycerin is present which is produced by hydrolysis in fixed oil which shows the presence of lipids.[34,35]

(K Ruckmani, et.al 2017) [34]

Test for Antioxidant Activity of Extracts:

Reducing Power method:

Principle –

This method is based on the principle of increase in the absorbance of the reaction mixture. Increase in the absorbance indicates increase in the antioxidant activity. In this, the antioxidant compound forms a coloured complex with potassium ferricyanide, trichloroacetic acid and ferric chloride, which is measured at 700nm. Increase in absorbance of reaction mixture indicates the reducing power of the samples.[36,37]

Determination of Viscosity:

Appartus: Brook Field Viscometer.

Principle: The viscosity is the most important parameter in the evaluation of cosmetic product. Viscosity governs the many properties such as spreadability, pourability of the product from the container. As viscosity is affected by many factors such as change in temperature, change in manufacturing condition, quality of the raw material. Hence it is very important to measure the viscosity of product.[38,39]

Procedure: The viscosity of serum was determined by using spindle no. 4 using brook field viscometer then all the operating conditions was set up. Then five readings were taken at different rpm and average of there will be the final reading. Viscosity was measured at 6 rpm in cps.

Determination of Spreadability Time:

Principle: It is very important for any cosmetic product that after application the product must be easily spread over the skin.[40,41] Spreadability is affected by many factors such as viscosity, temperature etc. The spreading time must be very less. The apparatus consist of a wodden block, with a movable glass slide with one end tied to weighted pan rolled on pulley. (Food U, et.al 2019)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Evaluation of Extract:****Preliminary Phytochemical Screening:****TABLE NO.3: PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING**

Sr. no.	Alkaloids	Flavonoids	Phenols	glycosides	Tannins	Lipids
1	Essential Oils	+	+	+	+	+

Here, + = Present, - = Absent

Evaluation Parameter of Containing Hair Growth Serum**TABLE NO: 4 EVALUATION PARAMETER OF CONTAINING HAIR GROWTH SERUM**

Sr.no	Parameters	Observation
1	Color	Colorless
2	Odor	Aromatic
3	Consistency	Good
4	pH	5.5±0.8
5	Viscosity	1050±0.2 centipoise
6	Spreadability	6.5±0.6 cm
7	Washability	Easily washable
10	Irritability	Non-irritant
11	Extrudability	15.3±1.2 g/cm ²

Vaccume Distillation

Result obtained by is shown in Table below

TABLE NO: 5 WEIGHT OF OIL WITH RESPECT TO TIME

Weight (g)	Time (mins)
0.40	250
0.45	500
0.50	750
0.55	100
0.65	1200

The oil produced by Vaccume Distillation Method is 2.55g weight of oil per 100g of dry Leaves Gotu Kola thereby producing 2.55% oil yield at 78⁰C.

Soxhletion Method

Result obtained by Soxhlet extraction is shown in Table below

TABLE NO: 6 WEIGHT OF OIL WITH RESPECT TO TIME

Weight of oil (g)	Time (mins)
0.5	250
0.6	500
0.7	750
0.90	1000
1.00	1200

The amount of pure Essential Gotu kola oil obtained by extraction method was 3.7g of essential oil per 100g of Rosemary roots sample. This gave 3.7% yield of essential oil. The volume of oil was measured at every 4hr interval to determine the oil yield at varying time. As the time increases the Ethanol solvent reduces thereby leaving the oil in the mixture.

TABLE NO: 7 RESULT OF ESSENTIAL OILS EXTRACTION

Method of extraction	% yield
vacuum Distillation	2.55
Soxhletion Method	3.7

Calculation of Percentage Yield of Volatile Oil.**Material Balance for Vacuum Distillation Method**

- Weight of Gotu Kola= 100g.
- Quantity of hexane used= 600ml, Quantity of Ethanol used= 200ml
- Weight of beaker= 105.26g.
- Weight ethanol and essential oil= 202.55g.
- The weight of oil obtained= 2.55g.
- %yield = ME/MG x 100.
- Where, ME = Mass of essential oil MG = Mass of Gotu Kola sample
- ME = 2.55g MG = 100g.
- By substituting values.
- %yield = 2.55/100 x 100 =2.55%.
- Therefore % yield= 2.55%.

The graph below shows the plot of the weight of essential oil with respect to time for solvent extraction method.

FIG NO: 4 GRAPH BELOW SHOWS THE PLOT OF THE WEIGHT OF ESSENTIAL OIL WITH RESPECT TO TIME FOR VACUUM DISTILLATION METHOD

Material Balance for Soxhletion Method

- Weight of Gotu kola leaves= 120g
- Quantity of Olive oil used= 600ml, Quantity of Ethanol used= 140ml
- Weight of beaker= 97.86g
- Weight ethanol and essential oil= 143.7g
- The total weight= 3.7g
- %yield = ME/Mg x 100
- Where
- ME = Mass of essential oil, MG = Mass of Gotu kola leaves Sample
- ME = 3.7g
- MR = 120g
- By substituting values
- %yield = 3.7/120 x 100 = 3.08%
- Therefore % yield= 3.08%
- Graph of the weight (g) of essential oil to the time (mins) for extraction method.

FIG NO 5 GRAPH OF THE WEIGHT (G) OF ESSENTIAL OIL TO THE TIME (MINS) FOR SOXHLETION METHOD

Patch test for Serum:

TABLE NO: 8 PATCH TEST OF SERUM

Sr.no.	Parameter	M1	M2
1	Immediately after removal of product	N.R.	N.R.
2	After 24 hrs	N.R.	N.R.
3	After 48 hrs	N.R.	N.R.

N.R = No Reaction

Stability study of serum

The sample of serum was kept at 5°C, room temperature 40°C. The changes in physical

appearance, colour, feel etc were studied.

TABLE NO.9: STABILITY STUDIES OF SERUM

SR.NO.	Parameters	M1	M2
1	Appearance	Opaque	Opaque
2	Colour	White	White
3	Spreadability	Good	Very good

CONCLUSION: The current work was done to prepare an anti-aging and anti-wrinkle Skin care serum using an appropriate base to form a skin care serum. The prepared skin care serum was evaluated using various parameters and was found to be satisfied with the application on the skin to make it healthy and glowing without any side effects. Since Ginger and Rosemary Flower is Essential anti-aging and anti-wrinkle agents, they are incorporated into the formulation which increases the efficiency of the product.

Shown strong anti-wrinkle, anti-aging activity, suitable SPF for skin to protect against UV rays and provide smooth Beautifying attractive appearance to skin with lustrous and cleansing effect. Moreover, the stability study has shown no significant effect on the viscosity, homogeneity and pH of all formulations. In summary, formulation has fulfilled the cosmoceutical requirements and considered safe for skin use.

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